

D2.1

Short report from the Nordic ESM diagnostics hackathon

Task leader: Øyvind Seland

Project manager: Anne Fouilloux

Work Package leader: Oskar Landgren

Internal reviewer: Tyge Løvset

Summary

The Earth System Model Evaluation Tool (ESMValTool) is a community diagnostics and performance metrics tool for the evaluation of Earth system Models (ESMs) that is not widely used in the Nordics yet. A hackathon/workshop was held on March 12, 2021 as a joint event between the INES, NICEST2 and IS-ENES3 projects. During this hackathon, we identified the needs for specific diagnostics for the Nordics that could help researchers to diagnose strengths and deficiencies of current ESMs. We also discussed how to better organize access to data and share resources within the Nordics.

Introduction

ESMValTool (<https://www.esmvaltool.org/>) is an open source project that is community driven and aims at facilitating sharing of diagnostic and performance metrics tools for routine evaluation of Earth system models in CMIP. ESMValTool is not widely used in the Nordics and apart from SMHI, very few researchers in the Nordics have used and/or developed diagnostics with it. One objective of NICEST2 is to encourage the usage of ESMValTool within the Nordic climate community and develop specific diagnostics for the Nordics. A hackathon/workshop was held on March 12, 2021 as a joint event between the INES, NICEST2 and IS-ENES3 projects to i) collect user requirements for diagnostic tools (ESMValTool, NCAR diagnostics, pyaerocom etc.) to support ESM model development in the Nordic countries (NorESM, EC-EARTH, ...); ii) exchange on current possibilities to use the ESMValTool and other tools on Nordic computing platforms in an efficient way; iii) explore ideas on developing a climate diagnostic ESMValTool module for the Nordic regions; iv) discuss other tools to enhance diagnostic capabilities (CMORization of model output on the fly for easy use of ESMValTool & other diagnostic libraries, Quicklooks for model development), multi-model evaluation scripts for CMIP6 analysis.

Report on the hackathon

25 people participated (out of 27 signed up) from four Nordic countries: Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden. The detailed program is available in Annex.

There was a general introduction to ESMValTool, including details about how to use it for diagnostics and evaluation of ESM data as well as contribute to the development. Then the participants shared their experiences with what they currently use in terms of tools, types of analyses, workflow etc. at the different institutes.

Presentations were also given about the implementation of ESMValTool on the Norwegian Nird HPC as well as efforts to run it in pan-Nordic context using Jupyterhub.

The participants were divided into three groups to discuss different topics. A brief summary of each group's discussion is outlined below:

1. How can the ESMValTool be used in Nordic cooperation projects? How to do efficient multi-model evaluations across groups?
 - One of the most important needs for doing multi-model analysis whether it is

using ESMValTool or other tools is to have easy access to data

- Should we try to aim for a common CMIP5 / CMIP6 database for data that we consider important for Nordic evaluation
- Likewise is it useful to have shared data for Nordic ESMs
 - Given a common database does it matter that the ESG nodes are at different tier levels? Linkøping (tier 0), CSC and Sigma2 (Tier 1) Does Linkøping mirror some of the data on the other sites anyway?
 - Given a common site should we be able to check who is using the data, in particular data that are not made publicly available on ESGF, but that we would like to share for common analysis
 - Will scratch functionality make it easier to have a common database (Automatic deletion of data that is not used)
 - Given common database(s) either of the data themselves or reference of existing CMIP6 experiments and analyses, how can we rapidly link to local analysis, e.g. of updated model versions or common model intercomparisons beyond CMIP style experiments.
 - Is it possible to use cloud resources, e.g. google cloud for analysis?
- Given a common storage are there enough resources to do the analysis - Do we need duplication/local copies for rapid access
- Do we need duplication for traceability
- If we want to use ESMValTool for common analysis, how good is the traceability in ESMValTool, what metadata information does ESMValTool write out
- How can we share information about existing analyses and / or access to existing analyses to avoid duplication of access.
 - ESMValTool can read it native EC-Earth data. Is it possible to extend this capability to NorESM and EC-HAM/ICONN or is it better to create more robust/automatic cmorization tools
- How can we cooperate for the best possible use and training and exchange of knowledge, modules and data both for ESMValTool but also for sharing of other tools. Are there common Nordic frameworks / projects that can promote this on a longer time-scale
- Is ESMValtool fast enough for quicklooks on new simulations, new users need to be able to read new model input without too much hassle.
- Is ESMValTool plots accepted as publication ready figures
- Collect information of what environments / tools are used in the Nordic countries - Should we be involved in development of / use of new data formats, e.g. datacube

format, zarr arrays (Pangeo) ?

<https://pangeo-data.github.io/pangeo-cmip6-cloud/>

2. User needs for a Nordic climate evaluation module for ESMValTool. Regionally specific indices etc.

- Users with background from different tools: Python, R, Matlab, ...
- Many concrete ideas for diagnostics were put forward:
 - AMOC (at meridional sections, not just 26.5N), ocean heat transport, mass transport across key domains (Denmark strait, Bering Strait), tracers
 - Trends in the ocean for the last 20 years (temperature, mixed layer depth)
 - Process based evaluations (EOFs) what is the dominant mode of variability and how that is related to NAO
 - Rain-on-snow events
 - Drought defined by soil moisture
 - Snow and vegetation (e.g., LAI, GPP)
 - Circulation indices, e.g. Scandinavian blocking, and blocking in general -

Observation datasets that can be included: Nordic flux measurements, Nordic Seas observations (spatially sparse but long time series on monthly frequency). - How to move forward with Nordic collaboration:

- Need a communication channel with low threshold for posting. Less formal than e.g. Github. Slack suggested. (See action point below.)
- Open to including work done by Nordic researchers focusing on other regions, e.g. Southern Ocean circulation, tropics, East African monsoon. - Consider using ESMValTool for new analyses (not necessarily rewriting old scripts).

3. Quicklook diagnostics for NorESM development

- Talked about why a quicklook diagnostic is needed for the ESM output: quick look of the model performance in an efficient way when the model is running and keep updating; do the diagnostics directly on the HPC platform, e.g., FRAM and Betzy instead of transferring temporary data back and forth
- Difficulties of running diagnostic on HPC
 - diagnostic tool is not designed to run in the backend compute node:

- bash, ncl scripts are not commonly parallelled;
- Login nodes have limited capacity for post-processing
 - Need a common disk area to store ~100 GB observational data
 - The current diagnostics running on NIRD have too many diagnostics; not needed for a quick look of model performance
- Possible solutions:
 - Make a light-weighted version of the NorESM Diagnostic Toolpackage (diag_run), with only some timeseries and climatology (average) plots.
 - Create a new set of NCO/CDO/NCL/python scripts/tools to make efficient diagnostics of key parameters/variables.
 - Comorize data and make use of ESMValTool???

Finally, there was a hands-on session to try out the ESMValTool. Users with an account on NIRD could do that on the NIRD machines directly, while external users used the NIRD toolkit (https://documentation.sigma2.no/nird_toolkit/overview_nird_toolkit.html) to access data originally stored on NIRD.

Action points

Each group identified a few action points, Some of these action points may not be followed up within NICEST-2 but have been listed for completion.

Group 1:

- Check if CMIP6 data is duplicated on many storage sites
- Check if any of the Nordic storage sites have resources to store and analyze data that is useful for Nordic intercomparison projects
- Make a survey to collect information about the tools used for ESM model analysis in the Nordic countries.

Group 2:

- There is a need for a low-threshold means of communication for people interested in using ESMValTool in the Nordics. Response: Tommi has now created a channel #esmvaltool-diagnostics on the NeIC Slack:
<https://neic.slack.com/archives/C01S8UQ2SRH>

Group 3:

- Organize an event on CMORization for users to cmorize their own experiments - Start a quick survey/poll if and how many people need to do cmorization for their own experiments: for sharing the model output with other researchers or for diagnosing the data with ESMValTool, etc.
- The event was held on June 8.
- Make an initial setup of the quicklook diagnostic toolkit for NorESM..... - Will start a small survey/document to collect important parameters/variables the model developers want to have for the quick diagnostics.

Conclusion

The hackathon allowed the participants to get a better understanding of the capabilities of ESMValTool and how it could be used by Nordic researchers. However, there is still a knowledge gap when it comes to using ESMValTool to develop new diagnostics. The first concrete action will be to create a slack channel under NeIC for having further internal discussions. The community also clearly raised the need for quicklook diagnostics that could also be run as soon as data is available e.g. even before its publication. This would require users to know how to CMORize ESM data and this is why the community plans to organize an event on CMORization.

Appendix: Invitation and programme

The following description and programme was displayed on the hackathon sign-up page:

Goals:

- Collect user requirements for diagnostic tools (ESMValTool, NCAR diagnostics, pyaerocom etc.) to support ESM model development in the Nordic countries (NorESM, EC-EARTH, ...).
- Exchange on current possibilities to use the ESMValTool and other tools on Nordic computing platforms in an efficient way.
- Explore ideas on developing a climate diagnostic ESMValTool module for the Nordic

regions. - Discuss other tools to enhance diagnostic capabilities (CMORization of model output on the fly for easy use of ESMValTool & other diagnostic libraries, Quicklooks for model development), multi-model evaluation scripts for CMIP6 analysis.

Agenda and presenters:

- 9:30 - 10:00 Introduction to ESMValTool. How can it be used? How can we contribute with our own analysis? (Klaus Zimmermann, SMHI)
- 10:00 - 10:30 Roundtable: What do you use at your institute? Tools, specific analysis scripts etc. (Open for short presentations from participants.)
- 10:30 - 10:40 Break
- 10:40 - 10:55 Local deployment of ESMValTool on Nird (Tomas Torsvik, UiB)
- 10:55 - 11:15 Towards a Nordic hub for joint evaluation of ESMs (Anne Fouilloux, UiO)
- 11:15 - 11:30 Discussion

Lunch break

- 12:30 - 13:50 Working groups (names of moderators):
1. How can the ESMValTool be used in Nordic cooperation projects? How to do efficient multi-model evaluations across groups? (Michael Schulz, MET Norway. Rapporteur Øyvind Seland, MET Norway)
 2. User needs for a Nordic climate evaluation module for ESMValTool. Regionally specific indices etc. (Oskar Landgren, MET Norway. Rapporteur Ada Gjermundsen, MET Norway)
 3. Quicklook diagnostics for NorESM development (Yanchun He, NERSC. Rapporteur Jan Griesfeller, MET Norway)
- 13:50 - 14:00 Break
- 14:00 - 14:30 Reporting from the groups and discussion
- 14:30 - 16:00 (Optional) Practical session trying out the ESMValTool on Nird (Jan Griesfeller, MET Norway)